

Capitalism, socialism and democracy; Schumpeter

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1. INTRODUCTION

Most political scholars accept THE CRITIQUE OF CLASSICAL DEMOCRATIC THEORY made in the previous chapter.

It is questioned that: "the people have a defined and rational opinion regarding all issues and that this opinion is expressed by the school of representatives who are in charge of its execution."

Therefore, the main objective of the DEMOCRATIC SYSTEM is questioned: "attributing to the electorate the power to decide on political matters" (the issue of the selection of representatives goes to a 2nd place).

THE DEMOCRATIC METHOD: is an institutional system for making political decisions, in which the individual acquires the power to decide through a competitive struggle for the votes of the voters.

2. THE DEMOCRATIC PROCESS THEORY

• A reasonably EFFICIENT CRITERIA is shown to distinguish a DEMOCRATIC GOVERNMENT from other different types. He questions whether the democratic government is the one that best serves the will and the good of the people.

x.eg The English parliamentary monarchy: takes the requirements of the democratic method because the monarch is limited to appointing the cabinet that the people themselves as parliament would elect.

VITAL ROLE OF "LEADERSHIP":

The COLLECTIVE BODIES act almost exclusively for the ACCEPTANCE OF THE LEADERSHIP. This is the dominant mechanism in practically all collective actions that are more than simple reflexes.

Statements about the functioning of the results of the democratic method that take this fact into account will be infinitely more realistic than propositions that ignore them.

THE COLLECTIVE BODIES "ARE NOT SATISFIED WITH THE EXECUTION OF THE GENERAL WILL".

THE MANUFACTURED WILL = It is the general will "substituted" or "falsified".

AUTHENTIC COLLECTIVE WILLS:

They are authentic, defined wills, sometimes very persistent over time, which a LEADER plus his assistants ORGANIZE, STIMULATE AND FINALLY INCLUDE IN THEIR ACTION PROGRAMS as appropriate incentives for their action plans.

THE INTERACTION BETWEEN REGIONAL INTERESTS AND PUBLIC OPINION and the way in which the set of circumstances that we call the "POLITICAL SITUATION" are produced appear, from this point of view, in a new and much clearer light.

THE CONCURRENCY:

In the struggle for leadership there is a concurrence, which in democracy means: "the free concurrence for the free vote."

Democracy implies a recognized method, through which a COMPETITIVE STRUGGLE is developed, being the ELECTORAL METHOD practically the only "equitable", whatever the size of the communities.

However, it gets worse by including many ways to obtain LEADERSHIP, which must be eliminated: "unfair, fraudulent or limited attendance".

But the cases mentioned cannot be excluded since we would be facing an "unreal or idealized democracy".

Cases of concurrence that are not duly democratic exist and lead to an "autocratic democracy." However, the study we are making of democracy will not take into account those fraudulent or corrupt aspects of it.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DEMOCRACY AND INDIVIDUAL FREEDOM:

"If all citizens were free to run for political leadership, standing for election, this would entail in most cases a considerable margin of freedom of expression for all".

In particular, it would mean a customary and extensive freedom of the press. This relationship between democracy and freedom is not absolutely rigid and can be modified. But from the intellectual point of view, it is despite what has been said, very important.

THE PRIMARY FUNCTION OF THE ELECTORATE IS TO FORM THE GOVERNMENT (directly or through an intermediate body), including also the POWER TO DISSOLVE IT.

- a) Form the Government: It simply means the acceptance of a leader or group of leaders.
- b) Power to dissolve it: The withdrawal of that acceptance.

But here too THE CONTROL OF POLITICAL LEADERS is raised: "If the electorate does not normally control its political leaders, except for the excuse of re-electing them, it is necessary to limit our ideas about that CONTROL in the manner indicated in our definition."

"On certain occasions REVOLUTIONS occur that bring down the government or an isolated minister, or force them to follow a certain line of action. These are not just exceptions, but also contrary to the democratic spirit.

PROPORTIONAL REPRESENTATION OR MAJORITY REPRESENTATION:

It is clear that the will of the majority (decided by decision of the majority of votes in Congress) IS NOT THE WILL OF THE PEOPLE.

It is obvious that proportional representation will not give opportunities to all types of idiosyncrasies, but it will prevent democracy from forming efficient governments and will constitute a danger in times of crisis.

Therefore, PROPORTIONAL REPRESENTATION does not imply a true representation of the people by the leader(s). And for this reason, the PRINCIPLE OF DEMOCRACY would imply that the reins of government should be handed over to those who have the greatest support from the other individuals or concurrent groups within politics.

3. THE APPLICATION OF THE "DEMOCRATIC" PRINCIPLE

Now we are going to deal with THE MOST IMPORTANT ASPECTS OF THE STRUCTURE AND FUNCTIONING OF THE POLITICAL MACHINE IN DEMOCRATIC COUNTRIES, in accordance with the Theory outlined in the preceding point:

- In democracies THE MAIN FUNCTION of the electorate is: "to elect the government". Limiting ourselves to the national government, we can say that the election of the government practically involves THE DECISION ON WHO WILL BE THE LEADER OR PRIME MINISTER.

But THE LEADER OR LEADING FIGURE should not mean that the persons so designated are endowed with leadership qualities and always lead personally.

There are favorable "political situations" in which men with poor leadership qualities can be elected and also unfavorable to the establishment of strong individual positions.

And it is recognized that it is a typical case of cause of political defeat.

USA: Method of democratic DIRECT ELECTION of the leader.

OTHER COUNTRIES: The electorate does not form the government "directly", but rather "indirectly" elects the members of Parliament. (The delegation of powers is not a logical evolution, but a natural one, whose meanings and results transcend official, if not legal, doctrines).

How is the Parliament or Government formed?:

In the Parliamentary System the Government is formed by the Parliament: The Parliament decides who will be the Prime Minister.

• What aspects influence the election of a Leader or a Political Party?:

-1- LEADERSHIP OF THE POLITICAL PARTY (LOYALTY TO THE PARTY).

-2- PARLIAMENT LEADERSHIP (sympathies of members of other political parties + chances of political success).

-3- LEADERSHIP OF PUBLIC OPINION: definitive success or "personal victory" of the Leader. EL LIDERAZGO DEL PRIMER MINISTRO:

It is made up of 3 elements that should not be confused and that are combined in different proportions depending on the case. This combination determines THE NATURE OF THE INDIVIDUAL DOMINANCE OF EACH PRIME MINISTER.

1st aspect: He is the Leader of his Political Party, not of Parliament (until he is invested).

2nd aspect: Once invested, he becomes Leader of the Parliament (it is like saying that he is the natural leader of the House of which he is a member (political party) and indirect of the other (Nation)). Either he acquires influence over the other parties, or he arouses their antipathy or that of their isolated members, which determines the importance of his chances of success in office.

3rd aspect: The Prime Minister will enjoy a leadership position different from that of the Party. He will constructively guide the opinion of the party, and in some cases will formulate it, and will finally rise to the direction of public opinion, to the national leadership, which seems to become to a certain extent, independent of the simple opinion of the party.

It goes without saying how personal such success is and how important SUPPORT OUTSIDE THE PARTY AND PARLIAMENT (PUBLIC OPINION) is.

THE PERSONAL VICTORY: This fact limits the previous affirmation that in a Parliamentary System the government is formed by the Parliament. In general, the Parliament decides who will be the Prime Minister but is not completely independent in this respect. Rather, it is highly influenced by the Public Opinion's ACCEPTANCE OF THE LEADER (the wishes of the members of Parliament are not the supreme condition of the process of electing the Government or the President, but rather they are guided by the Leader whom they will elect and by which they will be directed after being elected).

This personal relationship of leadership is the essence of the democratic method (public opinion) = PERSONAL VICTORY.

4. THE ATTRIBUTIONS OF THE CABINET

Curiously, this is a "double" body, which is the product of the Parliament and the Prime Minister as a whole.

The prime minister chooses its members, they are appointed and influence the prime minister's decisions; they are like a miniature parliament.

Whose function is an INTERMEDIATE LEADERSHIP, since they intervene in the matters dealt with in the Ministries, and are treated as a "dominant group", at the head of the bureaucratic machine.

It has great influence on general political decisions, however its relationship with respect to final decisions is distant, even when they are decisive in fulfilling the will of the people in each of the Ministries.

THE PARLAMENT:

We will define its main function: "CHOOSE AND DEFEAT GOVERNMENTS".

The first and most important OBJECTIVE of the Political Parties is "to defeat the other political parties and assume or maintain power". And his TOOL to achieve this is "inspired words on the issues under discussion".

THE VICTORY OVER THE ADVERSARY IS THE ESSENCE OF THE POLITICAL GAME.

IMPORTANT: Crucially therefore, regular parliamentary decision-making on national issues is the very method by which Parliament supports or refuses to support the government in power, or by which Parliament accepts or refuses to accept the leadership of the Prime Minister.

The Prime Minister is the person who selects from an incessant stream of daily issues those that he will transform into DISCUSSION ISSUES, that is: "those on which the Government is preparing to present bills or resolutions". And this is the factor that DOMINATES PARLIAMENTARY ACTIVITY.

But, to understand how democratic politics serves that social end, we must start from the "competitive struggle for power and office" and understand that the social function is taken just by accident, so to speak.

5. CONCLUSIONS

THE PSYCHOLOGY OF THE ADMINISTRATION AND PARTY PROPAGANDA, SLOGANS AND PATRIOTIC MARCHES are not, therefore, accessories but THE OWN ESSENCE OF POLITICS. In the same way, the POLITICAL CHIEF.

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